

Software Stack for ESMs– A Specification narrowing down D3.5 for the demonstrators

Deliverable D3.7

This project has received funding from the European Union's
Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme
under Grant Agreement No 675191

About this document

Work package in charge: WP3 Usability

Actual delivery date for this deliverable: February 2017

Dissemination level: PU (for public use)

Lead author:

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), Kim Serradell

Other contributing authors:

Max-Planck-Institut für Meteorologie (MPI-M), Reinhard Budich (Reviewer), Sergey Kosukhin

The University of Reading (UREAD), Grenville Lister

Contacts: esiwace@dkrz.de

Visit us on: www.esiwace.eu

Follow us on Twitter: [@esiwace](https://twitter.com/esiwace)

Disclaimer: This material reflects only the authors view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Index

1. Abstract /publishable summary	4
2. Conclusion & Results	4
3. Project objectives	4
4. Detailed report on the deliverable	5
5. References (<i>Bibliography</i>)	5
6. Dissemination and uptake.....	5
6.1 Dissemination	5
6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience	5
7. The delivery is delayed: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No.....	5
8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	5
9. Efforts for this deliverable	5
10. Sustainability.....	6
10.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date.....	6
10.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects	6
Software Stack for ESMs	7
INTRODUCTION	7
DEMONSTRATORS	7
SOFTWARE STACK.....	8
Common tools.....	8
Models.....	8
Installation.....	9
CONCLUSION	10

1. Abstract /publishable summary

Based on the work done in the scope of T3.1.3 in WP3 “Usability” and reported in D3.5 “How to Select, Configure and Install ESM Software Stacks”, in this document we will narrow the software stack needed to deploy and run the demonstrators defined in Work Package 2 “Scalability”. The goal is to build an exhaustive list of all the components needed by these ESMs to make the installation and execution as easy as possible.

2. Conclusion & Results

This document provides a complete list of software for all the demonstrators of ESIWACE project.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	Yes
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	Yes
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	No
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	No

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	No
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	Yes
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes

Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes
---	-----

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

This deliverable reports mainly work from BSC and MPI-M. BSC is responsible on EC-Earth demonstrator so, have experience in IFS/OpenIFS, NEMO and OASIS. MPI-M is one of the ICON developers and filled the requirements related to this model.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

Only user guides hosted in websites are referenced. For model references, please refer to other sections of the websites.

- OpenIFS user guide website: <https://software.ecmwf.int/wiki/display/OIFS/OpenIFS+user+guide>
- EC-Earth development portal: <https://dev.ec-earth.org/>
- NEMO user guide: <http://www.nemo-ocean.eu/Using-NEMO/User-Guides/Basics/NEMO-Quick-Start-Guide>
- OASIS user guide: http://www.cerfacs.fr/oa4web/oasis3-mct_3.0/oasis3mct_UserGuide.pdf
- Spack documentation: <https://spack.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Dissemination

This deliverable will be uploaded in the website. The list of software will be updated if there is a change in the demonstrator software stack. Information about the updates will be disseminated through the regular channels: project webpages, workshops and citations.

6.2 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is for:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

9. Efforts for this deliverable

Estimated person-months spent on this deliverable:

Beneficiary	Person-months	Period covered	Names of scientists involved, including third parties (if appropriate)
-------------	---------------	----------------	--

			and their gender (f/m)
DKRZ			
ECMWF			
CNRS-IPSL			
MPG	1	1 July 2016 – 28 February 2017	R. Budich (m), S. Kosukhin (m)
CERFACS			
BSC	1	1 July 2016 - 28 February 2017	K. Serradell (m), O. Mulla-Valls (m)
STFC			
MET O			
UREAD			
SMHI			
ICHEC			
CMCC			
DWD			
SEAGATE			
BULL			
ALLINEA			
Total	2		

10. Sustainability

10.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

Good collaboration between all the partners to build this deliverable. Each institution takes the responsibility of a model so it's easy to define the work of each. As a negative lesson, not in all models the information about requirements is easy to find. Some of them have a clear and understandable user guide and others not. Also, some requirements listed come from the experience of the partners when deploying ESMs.

10.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable is linked with WP3 "Usability" as it reflects the research done in the software stack for ESM and uses the new approaches in the automatic installation system using Spack. Is also linked with WP2 "Scalability" when it lists all the requirements of the demonstrators deployed in that work package. WP2 partners can take this report to easily install the demonstrators and all the tools needed to run and evaluate the performance.

Software Stack for ESMs

INTRODUCTION

This document summarizes and lists the software stack needed by the demonstrators defined in T2.2 of Scalability WP2. In this task, two global high-resolution model demonstrators have been defined:

1. Very high resolution atmosphere-only and ocean-only demonstrators.
2. High resolution coupled atmosphere-ocean demonstrators.

The main goal of the demonstrators is to show the computational capability of such high-resolution configurations. To reach this goal, not only the model itself has to be addressed but also the installation of all the tools and libraries needed.

In the document, we indicate the method of installation of each component. If the tool is available in the Spack¹ repository (see D3.5), it will be indicated. If not, the easiest way to install it will be described.

DEMONSTRATORS

The following models have been included as part of the demonstrators:

1. Very high resolution atmosphere-only and ocean-only demonstrators
 - IFS: Integrated Forecast System (developed by ECMWF)
 - ICON: Icosahedral non-hydrostatic general circulation model (developed by DWD, MPI-M and DKRZ)
 - NEMO: Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (developed by IPSL)
2. High resolution coupled atmosphere-ocean demonstrators
 - EC-Earth: European consortium developing a coupled climate model. The configuration analysed uses IFS for atmosphere, NEMO for ocean and OASIS for coupling.
 - ICON: as coupled climate model using its own ocean component ICON-OCE and the YAC coupler.

In the following section¹, we will list all the software needed to deploy and run these ESMs.

¹ <https://github.com/LLNL/spack>

SOFTWARE STACK

Common tools

Bash: all the models presented in this document are using bash or scripting related language in different stages of the execution. We consider this tool as standard on Unix/Linux systems.

Python and perl: these two tools are required also in many steps of the models' workflows. The models' workflow scripts are implemented using these two languages, therefore the corresponding interpreters are required to run them. The interpreters are available under names python and perl in the Spack repository, which also contains a collection of packages that extend their basic functionality.

Fortran and C compilers: many Linux/Unix systems come with gfortran/gcc by default which work well with the models. High Performance Computing facilities may provide other compilers which achieve better performance. The Fortran compiler must support an auto-double (e.g. -r8) capability as some source code files are in fixed format Fortran. OpenMP parallelism depends on each model.

MPI implementation: must be available on your system. It can either be vendor supplied or one of the freely available versions such as [MPICH](#) or [OpenMPI](#). The compatibility of each MPI implementation with the model should be checked with the model developers.

Performance measurement tools: the tools [Extræ](#) and [Paraver](#) are not required to run the models, but part of the work related to the demonstrators is to analyse the performance and the behaviours of the selected codes on HPC clusters. Extræ is the package devoted to generate Paraver trace-files for a post-mortem analysis. Extræ is a tool that uses different interposition mechanisms to inject probes into the target application so as to gather information regarding the application performance. Paraver is a very flexible data browser for trace files generated by Extræ. Paraver was developed to respond to the need to have a qualitative global perception of the application behaviour by visual inspection and then to be able to focus on the detailed quantitative analysis of the problems.

Models

Demonstrator	Model	Tool/Library	Version	Website	Package in Spack
Very high resolution atmosphere-only and ocean-only demonstrators	IFS/OpenIFS	LAPACK	3.4.2	http://www.netlib.org/lapack/	openblas
		BLAS	3.4.2	http://www.netlib.org/blas/	openblas
		GRIB-API	1.16.0	https://software.ecmwf.int/wiki/display/GRIB/Home	grib-api
		FCM	2015.03.0	http://metomi.github.io/fcm/doc/	NA
	NEMO	XIOS	2.0	http://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/ioserver/	NA

		NETCDF4	4.x	http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/	netcdf netcdf-fortran
		HDF5	1.8.x	https://support.hdfgroup.org/HDF5/	hdf5
		SZIP	2.1	https://www.hdfgroup.org/doc_resource/SZIP/	szip
		ZLIB	1.2.x	http://zlib.net	zlib
		FCM	2015.03.0	http://metomi.github.io/fcm/doc/	NA
	ICON	LAPACK	3.4.2	http://www.netlib.org/lapack/	openblas
		BLAS	3.4.2	http://www.netlib.org/blas/	openblas
		NETCDF4	4.x	http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/	netcdf-fortran
		HDF5	1.8.x	https://support.hdfgroup.org/HDF5/	hdf5
		SZIP	2.1	https://www.hdfgroup.org/doc_resource/SZIP/	szip
		ZLIB	1.2.x	http://zlib.net	zlib
		LIBXML2	2.9.x	http://xmlsoft.org	libxml2
		GRIB-API	1.16.0	https://software.ecmwf.int/wiki/display/GRIB/Home	grib-api

Demonstrator	Model	Component	Tool/Library	Version	Website	Package in Spack
High resolution coupled atmosphere-ocean demonstrators	EC-Earth	Atmosphere	IFS/Open IFS	see previous table		
		Ocean	NEMO	see previous table		
		Coupler	OASIS	3	https://verc.enes.org/oasis	NA
		Post-process	CDO	1.7.2	https://code.zmaw.de/projects/cdo	cdo py-cdo
	CMOR		3.0	http://cmor.llnl.gov/	cmor	
	ICON	Model	ICON	see previous table		
		Coupler	YAC	provided with the model		
		Post-process	CDO	1.7.2	https://code.zmaw.de/projects/cdo	cdo

Installation

Many of the used packages can be installed using Spack. This will reduce the complexity of the task. Spack will manage the dependencies, compilers and modules. Performance analysis tools Extrae and Paraver can also be installed using Spack. But some tools are not ported to this automatic method yet.

Packages not using automatic procedure installation are:

- FCM: FCM is a Perl script. It does not need sophisticated installation procedures, but only a list of Perl modules listed in the user guide.
- OASIS: to build OASIS, the makefile “TopMakefileOasis3” needs to be modified with regard to the common variables (path, compiler and libraries). Executing “make -f

TopMakefileOasis3 oasis3 psmile" will build the software. Please refer to chap. 8.1.1 in the user guide to get more information.

- YAC: YAC is provided along with ICON. Its compilation and installation is handled by the model's building system.

CONCLUSION

We presented the list of the software needed to build and run the models designed as demonstrators. Most of the software is covered with the automatic tool Spack. An effort remains to finish and cover all the libraries and tools needed and evaluate the feasibility of install the models themselves using Spack. This will be attempted in the next reporting period.